

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D2.4 Report from desk review of RAs and IRBs

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

Grant Agreement no.: 101103296

Lead contractor for this deliverable: Uganda National Drug Authority

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Project Acronym:	ACCESSAFRICA 2
Project Title:	Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa
Title of Deliverable:	D2.4 Report from desk review of RAs and IRBs
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Reviewer(s):	Florence Wanyenze and Kenneth Mugisa
Report Approved by	Dr. Helen Byomire Ndagije

Consortium Partners:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organisation	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

BACKGROUND

One of the objectives for Work Package 2, 'To support the implementation of the recommendations from the WHO Global Benchmarking exercise in the oversight of clinical trials' includes revising the existing tools and guidelines on the conduct of clinical trials to incorporate safety requirements for emerging technologies which revision will also aim to harmonize clinical trial reporting and transitioning to the AVAREF templates for assessment and inspection.

A copy of the copy of the desk review report is submitted as an attachment to this report.

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EVALUATOR'S REPORT FOR NEW CLINICAL TRIAL APPLICATIONS

Clinical Trial Application Number:CTA 0260

Evaluators: Kenneth Mugisa **Signature:**MK..... **Date:**29/02/2024.....

Florence Wanyenze **Signature:**FW **Date:**29/02/2024.....

Study Title	A Phase III, Multicenter, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-controlled Study evaluating the Efficacy and Safety of Inavolisib in combination with Phesgo versus Placebo in combination with Phesgo as maintenance therapy after first line induction therapy in participants with PIK3CA-mutated HER2-Positive locally advanced or Metastatic breast cancer (INAVO122)
Short title/Acronym (Where applicable)	INAVO122
Protocol Number	WO44263
Version Number and Date	Version 1.0 dated 16 11 2022
Investigational Medicinal Product	1. Inavolisib (RO7113755) Inavolisib is not registered.
IMP Manufacturer	
National PI Name, Address and Contact	

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Sponsor Name, Address and Contact	
Data Safety Monitoring Board chair, Name, Address and Contact	
Sponsor-appointed Monitor	
Applicant Name, Address and Contact	

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ADMINISTRATIVE

Issue	Workspace and Evaluator's comment
1. Declaration by the applicant, Principal Investigator and study monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signature for declaration of intent by applicant confirmed present. • Signed declaration by PI submitted. • Signed declaration by study monitor submitted. <p>Comment: All the required declarations are duly signed including the declaration on funds for clinical trial</p>
2. Details of the investigators	<div style="background-color: #4F81BD; height: 150px; width: 100%;"></div> <p>The investigators are qualified by education, training and experience to assume responsibility for the proper conduct of the study. The study team also includes an oncologist</p> <p>Clinical trial agreement is still in draft format and not signed</p>
3. Details of the site(s)	<p>The site is Uganda Cancer Institute Upper Mulago Hill Road</p>

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	Telephone Tel: +256 414 540 410
	The study has one site at in Uganda. (Uganda Cancer Institute)
4. Capacity of the site(s)	<p>CTA section 4.2.2</p> <p>The site study staff is made up of Study physician, pharmacists Laboratory technician and Study Nurse. 7 CVs for the key study personnel has been submitted.</p> <p>An area has been designated for research with 2 clinical rooms, one counselling room, a coordination room, a data room, two waiting areas and a research pharmacy where The Medicines and Placebo are to be stored. Emergency room with associated equipment is also available</p> <p>The site is stated to have adequate facilities for the study.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Applicant should submit an accreditation certificate for the on-site laboratory which will run safety assessments at the Uganda Cancer Institute 2. The accreditation certificate for one of the laboratories, Cellcarta, Sint-BAVOSTRAAT 78-80 B-2610-Belgium had expired on 10/25/2023
5. Insurance	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Certificate of Jubilee Allianz General Insurance, policy number 80000000/2023/243, period of insurance from 01/07/2023 to 31/12/2031. The policy is a No-Fault compensation for clinical trials. It is study specific.</p> <p>Comment</p>

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	<p>Clinical trial insurance is Considered adequate. However, no professional indemnity has been submitted (applicant stated that all investigators are working at the Uganda Cancer Institute which is a Government Institute so do not require the Malpractice Insurance)</p>
6. IMP Handling	<p>CTA section 3.3 and CT protocol section 6.1.1 and 6.1.2</p> <p>Sponsors will ship All trial drugs and delivered directly to the site. However, clearing and handling will be done by Laborex Uganda. Laborex has extensive experience in handling IP and has sufficient storage capacity to maintain cold chain.</p> <p>Dispensing and accountability details are provided in the pharmacy manual. Waste disposal will be done according to UCI guidelines also attached.</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Adequate details have been provided.</p>
7. Duration of the trial	<p>The study is expected to last up to 111 months after the first participant is enrolled.</p> <p>Duration for individual participant; Induction phase - 4-8 cycles of taxanes and PH or phesgo, maintenance phase: up to a survival event as defined in the protocol or end of study.</p>
	<p>Estimated duration of the trial: is expected to occur approximately 111 months after the first participant is enrolled.</p>
8. Ethics	<p>Joint review submission to UCIREC, UNCST and NDA</p>

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	<p>This study is to be performed in compliance with US CFR guidelines, International Council for Harmonization (ICH) and applicable Good Clinical Practices (GCPs) and federal and local regulations</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Applicant is expected to submit ethical approval and UNCST after the joint review</p>
<p>9. Training</p>	<p>CTA section 7.3</p> <p>Local Staff and Investigators have been trained in both GCP and HSP, they will further receive refresher protocol training before implementing the trial.</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Considered adequate</p>
<p>10. Study monitoring</p>	<p>CT protocol section 8.10.10 and appendix 1</p> <p>Sponsor monitors and auditors will have direct access to appropriate parts of records relating to an individual's participation in the RBR for the purposes of verifying the data provided to the Sponsor. The site will permit monitoring, audits, IRB/EC review, and health authority inspections by providing direct access to source data and documents related to the RBR samples. Study monitors will perform ongoing monitoring activities as specified in the Trial Monitoring Plan to confirm that data entered into the CRF by authorized site personnel are accurate, complete, and verifiable from source documents; that the safety and rights of participants are being protected; and that the study is being</p>

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	<p>conducted in accordance with the currently approved protocol and any other study agreements, the ICH Guideline for Good Clinical Practice, and all applicable regulatory requirements.</p>
<p>11. Data management</p>	<p>Study monitoring details for the monitor have been provided</p> <p>The study monitor's declaration is duly signed</p> <p>Applicant to submit the monitoring plan for this study</p>
<p>12. Submission to other regulatory authorities</p>	<p>The study has received "No objection letter "from health Canada</p> <p>200–220 sites globally will participate to enrol approximately 230 participants. No details of these global sites have been proved</p> <p>This study will be implemented in Canada among other countries</p> <p>Applicant to clarify on the exact countries (other sites) will implement this study</p>
<p>13. History of previous trials</p>	<p>HEREDERA study WO43571 - a phase iii, randomized, open-label study evaluating the efficacy and safety of giredestrant in combination with phesgo versus phesgo after induction therapy with phesgo+taxane in patients with previously untreated her2- positive, estrogen receptor-positive locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer.</p>

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	The study was recently approved by NDA in December 2023.
14. Registration in any known Clinical Trial Registry	EU Trial Number: 2022-502046-28-00 Clinicaltrials.gov number: NCT05894239
	PACTR number not provided

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CLINICAL ASSESSMENT

Issue	Workspace and Evaluator's comment
1. Rationale for the study	<p>Study protocol section 2.1 and</p> <p>Approximately 25%–30% of HER2--positive breast cancers harbor PIK3CA-mutations that result in dysregulation of the PI3K pathway, serve as a negative prognostic biomarker, and sensitize nonclinical models to PI3K inhibition. Multiple studies implicate the PI3K pathway in resistance to HER2-targeted therapies and suggest that the addition of a PI3Kα inhibitor to trastuzumab and pertuzumab may improve outcomes for participants with PIK3CA-mutated HER2-positive ABC. Inavolisib is a potent, selective inhibitor of the Class I PI3Kα isoform (p110α), with more than 300-fold less potent biochemical inhibition of the Class I PI3K β, γ, and δ isoforms and increased potency in tumor cells bearing <i>PIK3CA</i>-mutations over cells without <i>PIK3CA</i>-mutations. The study will assess the efficacy and safety of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo (pertuzumab, trastuzumab, and rHuPH20 injection, for subcutaneous use) in participants with previously untreated phosphatidylinositol- 4,5-biphosphate 3-kinase catalytic subunit α (PIK3CA)-mutated, HER2-positive locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer (advanced breast cancer, ABC) as maintenance therapy.</p> <p>The rationale provided by the sponsor is acceptable</p>
2. Product information	
2.1 Properties of drug	<p>The IMP for the study is inavolisib (RO7113755)</p> <p>Inavolisib (RO7113755)</p>

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	<p>Invasolib is apotent selective inhibitor of the Class I PI3K alpha isoform (p110) that specifically triggers the degradation of mutant p110 alpha, as an anti-cancer agent. Nonclinical studies demonstrate that Inavolisib specifically triggers the degradation of mutant p110 alpha, inhibits proliferation and induces apoptosis of PIK3CA-mutant breast cancer cell lines, inhibits tumor growth in human breast cancer xenograft models harboring PIK3CA mutations, and reduces downstream PI3K pathway markers. Efficacy was improved when Inavolisib was used in combination with standard-of-care therapies for breast cancer, including paclitaxel (chemotherapy), fulvestrant (endocrine therapy), or palbociclib (CDK4/6 inhibitor), in a PIK3CA-mutated human breast cancer xenograft model.</p>
	<p>Adequate details are provided.</p>
<p>2.2 Non-clinical findings</p>	<p>In Vitro Studies</p> <p>PI3K Isoform Biochemical Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1792)</p> <p>In a biochemical assay, inavolisib was shown to be a potent inhibitor of PI3Kα. Inavolisib is 2676-fold more potent against PI3Kα than PI3Kβ, 337-fold more potent against PI3Kα than PI3Kδ, and 574-fold more potent against PI3Kα than on PI3Kγ</p> <p>Kinase Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1794)</p> <p>Inavolisib was tested in the Invitrogen kinase panel and found to have high specificity for PI3K. Inavolisib inhibited 3 of 224 kinases in the Invitrogen kinase panel at > 80% at 1 μM. Two of the kinases, PI3Kα and PI3Kγ, are targets of inavolisib</p> <p>Mutant Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1793)</p>

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Inavolisib is a potent PI3K inhibitor in SW48 cells and demonstrated a stronger effect in SW48 lines that were engineered to harbor a *PIK3CA* mutation. When assayed by the pPRAS40 assay, inavolisib was 2.4-fold more potent in E545K cells and 2.6-fold more potent in H1047R cells relative to the *PIK3CA*-WT parental cells

Inavolisib Activity in HER2+ Breast Cancer Cells

Inavolisib-induced mutant p110 α degradation is enhanced by receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) activity and provides benefit in HER2+ p110 α -mutated cancers.

In Vivo Studies

Single Agent Efficacy and Pharmacodynamics

Nonclinical studies were conducted to determine whether PO QD dosing of inavolisib as a single agent in vivo is efficacious against orthotopic (mammary fat pad) human KPL-4 (13-3399 L) or HCC1954x1 (13-3399 O) breast cancer xenografts in immunodeficient mice. In both studies, dose-dependent TGI was observed, with the highest TGI noted at the MTD. In Study 13-3399 L, all doses were tolerated. For Study 13-3399 O, all doses were well tolerated with the exception of 50 mg/kg.

Efficacy of Inavolisib in Combination with Standard-of-Care Therapies

Inavolisib was tested in nonclinical studies to evaluate efficacy in combination with standard-of-care drugs such as palbociclib (16-0598, 16-2204), fulvestrant (16-0599, 16-2204), paclitaxel (16-0600), trastuzumab plus pertuzumab (18-1388 J) or T-DM1 (18-1388 D). In the doublet studies (16-0598, 16-0599, 16-0600), inavolisib was evaluated as a single agent or in combination with palbociclib, SC fulvestrant, or intravenous (IV) paclitaxel. Inavolisib and palbociclib were administered PO QD, and

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fulvestrant and paclitaxel were delivered weekly (QW), with all agents dosed for 21 days. At the end of treatment, each combination resulted in increased TGI when compared with the respective single agents (see Appendix 1 for details). Overall, the tested drug combinations of inavolisib with standard-of-care therapies were tolerated.

No pharmacodynamic drug interaction studies were done on inavolisib

Safety Pharmacology

In the single-dose cardiovascular safety pharmacology study in dogs (15-3293), inavolisib-related cardiovascular effects included generally dose-dependent, reversible, and non-adverse decreases in heart rate, increases in arterial pressure and contractility, lengthening of PR and QT intervals (likely driven by the decreased heart rates), and minimally lengthened QTc at doses ≥ 0.3 mg/kg.

Phototoxicity

Inavolisib absorbs light in the ultraviolet range and has been shown to distribute to the skin and eye in a rat quantitative whole-body radiography study (18-2298), thus the potential for phototoxicity was assessed. In the neutral red uptake phototoxicity assay in BALB/c 3T3 mouse fibroblasts (3T3 cells), inavolisib did not show phototoxicity potential (16-1227).

Toxicology and Safety Pharmacology Integrated Analyses

The DLTs identified in nonclinical toxicology studies were consistent with the anticipated pharmacologic effects of PI3K inhibition, and included hyperglycemia and body weight loss in rats and dogs, and inflammation in dogs. In addition, bone marrow hypocellularity, atrophy of glandular and

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	<p>reproductive tissues and eye lens degeneration were observed in the rats; and lymphoid depletion and swelling of the lens fibers in the eye were observed in the dogs.</p> <p>Fetal malformations and variations observed in rats warrant the continued use of highly effective contraception in clinical trials utilizing inavolisib.</p> <p>No human-specific metabolites were detected in liver microsomes. in single dose toxicity MTD of inavolisib in rats after a single dose was determined to be 30 mg/kg, the highest dose tested.</p> <p>The dose limiting toxicities (DLTs) identified in nonclinical toxicology studies were consistent with the anticipated pharmacologic effects of PI3K inhibition, and included hyperglycemia and body weight loss in rats and dogs, and inflammation in dogs. In addition, bone marrow hypocellularity, atrophy of glandular and reproductive tissues and eye lens degeneration were observed in the rats; and lymphoid depletion and swelling of the lens fibers in the eye were observed in the dogs.</p> <p>Inavolisib administration in dogs for up to 3 months was associated with dose-dependent and reversible inflammation in multiple organs and correlating clinical pathology changes of inflammatory markers.</p> <p>Decreases in lymphocytes in lymphoid tissues were observed in dogs given inavolisib for 28 days and were anticipated on the basis of inhibition of the PI3K pathway, which regulates cell proliferation and differentiation.</p> <p>The no observable effect level (NOAEL) for maternal toxicity is considered to be 6 mg/kg/day (the highest dose tested).</p> <p>From the pre-clinical studies, the IMP demonstrated efficacy. Some adverse events were noted that have been addressed in the risk management plan (appendix 4 of the protocol).</p>
<p>2.3 Clinical findings</p>	<p>Absorption, Bioavailability, Distribution, Metabolism, and Elimination</p>

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Time to maximum concentration of inavolisib occurred approximately 3 hours (median) after a single dose as well as at steady state. Mean half-life ($t_{1/2}$) calculated across dose levels following a single dose was approximately 16 hours (range: 9-33 hours).

Pharmacokinetics of Metabolites

In preliminary studies using plasma samples collected from patients during Phase I (Study GO39374), two metabolites (amide hydrolysis; di-oxidation) representing less than 1% of the total drug-related exposure each were detected. In Study GP42652, circulating metabolites were minimal with the majority (99.5%) of drug-related material being inavolisib. The major metabolic pathway was hydrolysis of the primary amide to carboxylic acid (22-0069).

Clinical efficacy

As of 1 April 2022, there were 195 efficacy-evaluable patients in the Phase I Study GO39374 (defined as any patient with at least one dose of any study treatment) and 166 efficacy-evaluable patients with measurable disease per RECIST v1.1 at baseline. Among the 195 efficacy-evaluable patients, the objective response rate (ORR; confirmed CR or PR) was 23% (44 patients), and the best objective response rate (BOR rate; confirmed or unconfirmed CR or PR) was 29% (56 patients). Three patients had confirmed CRs (two patients with measurable disease and one patient with non-measurable disease); all other responses were PRs. Among the 166 efficacy-evaluable patients with measurable disease, the ORR was 26% (43 patients), and the BOR rate was 33% (55 patients). Among these patients, 2 patients had confirmed CRs; all other responses were PRs.

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The median investigator-assessed PFS per RECIST v1.1 for the 195 efficacy-evaluable patients was 9.1 months (95% CI: 7.1, 11.0) with 69% of patients (135 patients) experiencing an event of disease progression or death

Grade 3-5 AEs

Grade ≥ 3 AEs, regardless of attribution, occurring in $\geq 3\%$ of patients (i.e., ≥ 6 patients) overall were: neutropenia (46 patients, 24%; including AE term neutrophil count decreased), hyperglycemia (45 patients, 23%), anemia (12 patients, 6%), lymphopenia and fatigue (10 patients each, 5%), aspartate aminotransferase increased, hypokalemia, nausea, and leukopenia (8 patients each, 4%), and hypophosphatemia and thrombocytopenia (7 patients each, 4%).

Adverse Events Attributed to Study Treatment

Overall, AEs attributed to any study drug (except metformin) by the investigators were reported in 185 (95%) of patients. AEs attributed to any study drug (except metformin) occurring in $\geq 20\%$ of patients (i.e., ≥ 39 patients) were: hyperglycemia (126 patients, 65%), diarrhea (83 patients, 43%), nausea (69 patients, 35%), neutropenia (60 patients, 31%; includes AE term of neutrophil decreased), stomatitis (56 patients, 29%), decreased appetite (46 patients, 24%), fatigue (40 patients, 21%), and dysgeusia (39 patients, 20%).

The following SAEs were related to involisib

Hyperglycemia, cellulitis, confusional state, osteomyelitis, periodontal disease, rash, diarrhea, stomatitis, panniculitis, vomiting.

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	<p>Effects on QTcF and Cardiac Adverse Events</p> <p>QT/QTc prolongation risk of inavolisib was investigated with the preliminary data from Study GO39374. The clinical C-QTc data together with the in vitro hERG data (Section 4.3.8), suggest a low risk of QT interval prolongation when patients are administered 9 mg QD of inavolisib.</p> <p>In summary the following risks are associated with inavolisib</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyperglycemia • Stomatitis /oral mucositis • Gastrointestinal toxicities • Skin disorders <p>The clinical data shows an efficacy ranging from 22% to 33%. This could be acceptable for cancer. The safety profile indicates some adverse events as detailed above. These have been considered in the risk management plan (appendix 4 of the protocol).</p> <p>An updated IB should be provided that avails current data. The one submitted is version Number 7, dated August 2022. It provides data upto May 2022.</p>
<p>2.4 Systematic reviews and/or citations.</p>	<p>No peer reviewed articles were submitted.</p> <p>PI to submit peer reviewed articles</p>
<p>3. Objectives and endpoints</p>	

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<p>3.1 Primary objectives and endpoints (Outcome measurements/variables)</p>	<p>CT protocol section 3:</p> <p>Objective: To demonstrate PFS (Progression Free Survival) superiority of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo over placebo in combination with Phesgo</p> <p>Endpoint: Time from randomization to the first occurrence of a PFS event assessed by the investigator according to RECIST v1.1 or death from any cause (whichever occurs first)</p> <p>The primary objective is clearly defined and measurable and acceptable. The primary endpoint is acceptable and aligns with primary objective.</p>							
<p>3.2 Secondary objectives and endpoints</p>	<p>CT protocol section 3:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="618 842 2060 1327"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="618 842 1341 879">Objective</th> <th data-bbox="1341 842 2060 879">Endpoint</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="618 879 1341 994">To evaluate OS of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared to placebo in combination with Phesgo</td> <td data-bbox="1341 879 2060 994">Time from randomization to death from any cause</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="618 994 1341 1327">To evaluate the efficacy of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo</td> <td data-bbox="1341 994 2060 1327"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORR (following randomization), defined as the proportion of participants with a CR or PR on two consecutive occasions ≥ 4 weeks apart, as assessed by the investigator according to RECIST v1.1 • DOR (following randomization), defined as the time from the first occurrence of a documented objective response to disease progression as assessed by the investigator </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Objective	Endpoint	To evaluate OS of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared to placebo in combination with Phesgo	Time from randomization to death from any cause	To evaluate the efficacy of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORR (following randomization), defined as the proportion of participants with a CR or PR on two consecutive occasions ≥ 4 weeks apart, as assessed by the investigator according to RECIST v1.1 • DOR (following randomization), defined as the time from the first occurrence of a documented objective response to disease progression as assessed by the investigator
Objective	Endpoint							
To evaluate OS of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared to placebo in combination with Phesgo	Time from randomization to death from any cause							
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		<p>according to RECIST v1.1, or death from any cause (whichever occurs first)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CBR (following randomization), defined as the proportion of participants with SD for ≥ 24 weeks or a CR or PR, as assessed by the investigator according to RECIST v1.1 • PFS2, defined as the time from randomization to disease progression as assessed by the investigator or death from any cause (whichever occurs first) during or following the first non-protocol mandated anti-cancer treatment • Mean and mean changes from baseline score in function and HRQoL by cycle and between treatment arms as assessed through the use of the Functional (Role, Physical) and GHS/QoL scales of the EORTC QLQ-C30
	<p>To evaluate the safety of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence and severity of adverse events, with severity determined according to NCI PRO-CTCAE Version 5.0 grading scale • Change from baseline in targeted clinical laboratory test results
	<p>To characterize the pharmacokinetics of inavolisib</p>	<p>Plasma concentration of inavolisib at specified timepoints</p>

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	The secondary objectives are clearly defined and measurable and are acceptable. The endpoints are acceptable and in line with the Secondary objective.		
3.3 Exploratory or tertiary objectives and endpoints	CT protocol section 3:		
	SN	Tertiary objective	Tertiary endpoint
	1.	To evaluate the efficacy of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean and mean changes from baseline score in remaining function scales and disease/ treatment-related symptoms by cycle and between treatment arms as assessed by the EORTC QLQ-C30 and EORTC QLQ-BR23. • Mean and mean changes from baseline score in the “worst pain” item from the Brief Pain Inventory-Short Form (BPI-SF).
	2.	To evaluate effects of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo on work productivity and activity	Changes in participant reported Work Productivity and Activity Impairment Questionnaire (WPAI) scores at specified timepoints
	3.	To evaluate health utility of participants treated with inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared with placebo in combination with Phesgo to generate utility scores for use in economic models	Health utility and visual analog score of the European Quality of Life 5-Dimension, 5 Level (EQ-5D-5L) questionnaire
	4.	To evaluate the tolerability of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo compared	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence, frequency of occurrence, severity, and/or degree of interference with daily function

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		with placebo plus Phesgo from the participants perspective	<p>of symptomatic treatment toxicities (i.e., nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, rash, fatigue, decreased appetite, mouth or throat sores), as assessed through use of the NCI PRO-CTCAE.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of participants reporting each response option at each assessment timepoint by treatment arm for treatment side-effect bother single-item GP5 from the FACT-G. • Change from baseline in proportion of participants reporting symptomatic treatment toxicities and treatment side-effect bother, as assessed through use of the PRO-CTCAE and the overall treatment side-effect bother single-item GP5, respectively
	5.	To evaluate potential relationships between drug exposure and the efficacy and safety of inavolisib plus Phesgo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationship between plasma concentrations or PK parameters for inavolisib and efficacy endpoints at specified timepoints • Relationship between plasma concentrations or PK parameters for inavolisib and safety endpoints at specified timepoints
	6.	To evaluate potential relationships between selected covariates and inavolisib exposure when given in combination with Phesgo	Relationship between selected covariates and plasma concentration or PK parameters for inavolisib
	7.	To characterize the pharmacokinetics of trastuzumab and pertuzumab	Serum concentrations of trastuzumab and pertuzumab at specified timepoints

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	8.	To evaluate the anti-drug antibodies (ADA) to trastuzumab, pertuzumab, and rHuPH20	Prevalence of ADAs at baseline and incidence of ADAs during the study
	9.	To evaluate potential effects of ADAs with Phesgo	Relationship between ADA status and efficacy, safety, or PK endpoints
	10.	<p>To identify and/or evaluate biomarkers that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • are associated with response to study treatment (i.e., predictive biomarkers) • are associated with progression to a more severe disease state (i.e., prognostic biomarkers) • are associated with acquired resistance to the study treatment, are associated with susceptibility to developing adverse events or can lead to improved adverse event monitoring or investigation (i.e., safety biomarkers) • can provide evidence of study treatment activity (i.e., pharmacodynamic biomarkers) • can increase the knowledge and understanding of disease biology and drug safety or PK 	Relationship between biomarkers in tumor tissue and blood and efficacy, safety, PK, or other biomarker endpoints

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	<p>The tertiary objectives are clearly defined, measurable and acceptable. The endpoints are acceptable and in line with the tertiary objectives.</p> <p>The seventh objective on characterising PK of trastuzumab and pertuzumab could cause additional burden to the participants as it may require withdraw of more blood from participants.</p>
<p>4. Study population</p>	
<p>4.1 Inclusion criteria</p>	<p>CT protocol section 5.3</p> <p>Potential participants are eligible to participate in the induction and/or maintenance therapy of the study, only if all of the following criteria described in Section 5.1 apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signed Informed Consent Form • Age ≥ 18 years at the time of signing Informed Consent Form • If female, individuals must meet at least one of the following definitions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Postmenopausal, as defined by listed criteria: ○ Premenopausal or perimenopausal are defined as women not meeting the criteria for postmenopausal. Ability to comply with the study protocol in the investigator's judgment • Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) Performance Status 0 or 1 • Histologically or cytologically confirmed and documented adenocarcinoma of the breast with metastatic or locally advanced disease not amenable to curative resection. • Consent to provide archival tumor tissue specimen from the primary tumor or metastatic sites to assess biomarker eligibility. It is preferred that the specimen be from the most recently collected

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	<p>and available tumor tissue, and whenever possible, from a recurrence or metastatic site of disease. Only participants who do not have tissue specimens that meet eligibility requirements may undergo a biopsy during biomarker screening.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Confirmation of HER2 biomarker eligibility based on valid results from central testing of tumor tissue documenting HER2-positivity. Local test results are not acceptable for HER2 biomarker eligibility determination.• Confirmation of PIK3CA-mutation biomarker eligibility based on valid results from central testing of tumor tissue documenting PIK3CA-mutated tumor status. Local test results are not acceptable for PIK3CA-mutation biomarker eligibility determination.• Documented either HR-positive (ER+ and/or PR+) or HR-negative breast cancer according to American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO)/College of American Pathologists (CAP) guidelines (Allison et al. 2020) based on local assessment of the most recent (preferred) or archival tumor tissue sample. HR-positive tumor is ER-positive and/or progesterone receptor-positive, defined as $\geq 1\%$ of tumor cells stained positive for the respective receptor.• Disease-free interval from completion of adjuvant or neoadjuvant systemic non-hormonal treatment to recurrence of ≥ 6 months• At least one measurable lesion and/or non-measurable disease evaluable according to RECIST version 1.1• Participants who receive induction therapy prior to study enrollment: baseline tumor assessments must meet the criteria as listed in Section 4.1.2.• Participants with CNS metastases are eligible, provided they meet defined criteria:
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	<p>Inclusion criteria are well defined and satisfactory. The inclusion puts into consideration biomarkers, informed consent, receptors, Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction, liver function among others</p>
<p>4.2 Exclusion criteria</p>	<p>CT protocol section 5.2:</p> <p>Potential participants are excluded from both induction and maintenance therapy of the study if any of the following criteria apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior treatment in the locally advanced or metastatic setting with any PI3K, AKT, or mTOR inhibitor or any agent whose mechanism of action is to inhibit the PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathway. • Any prior systemic non-hormonal anti-cancer therapy for locally advanced or metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer prior to initiation of induction therapy • Disease progression within 6 months of receiving any HER2-targeted therapy • Type 2 diabetes requiring ongoing systemic treatment at the time of study entry; or any history of Type 1 diabetes • Inability or unwillingness to swallow pills • Malabsorption syndrome or other condition that would interfere with enteral absorption • History or active inflammatory bowel disease (e.g., Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis) or chronic diarrhea • Participants currently receiving immunosuppressants (e.g., sulfasalazines) are considered to have active disease and are therefore ineligible Clinically significant and active liver disease, including severe liver impairment (Child-Pugh Class B or C), active viral or other hepatitis (e.g., hepatitis B or hepatitis C), autoimmune hepatic disorders, sclerosing cholangitis, current alcohol abuse, or cirrhosis

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • History of or active clinically significant cardiovascular dysfunction as defined in criteria. • Requirement for daily supplemental oxygen • Symptomatic active lung disease, including pneumonitis or interstitial lung disease • Any history of leptomenigeal disease or carcinomatous meningitis • Uncontrolled pleural effusion, pericardial effusion, or ascites requiring recurrent drainage procedures every 2 weeks or more frequently • Indwelling pleural or abdominal catheters may be allowed, provided the participant has adequately recovered from the procedure, is hemodynamically stable and symptomatically improved • Any concurrent ocular or intraocular condition (e.g., cataract or diabetic retinopathy) that, in the opinion of the investigator, would require medical or surgical intervention during the study period to prevent or treat vision loss that might result from that condition • Active inflammatory (e.g., uveitis or vitritis) or infectious (e.g., conjunctivitis, keratitis, scleritis, or endophthalmitis) conditions in either eye or history of idiopathic or autoimmune-associated uveitis in either eye • Serious infection requiring IV antibiotics within 7 days prior to Day 1 of Cycle 1
<p>5. Study design</p>	<p>The exclusion criteria are acceptable. Precautions in the IB have been put into consideration</p>
<p>5.1 General considerations</p>	<p>CT protocol section 4.1.2</p> <p>Study WO4423 is a Phase III, multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled global study designed to compare the efficacy and safety of inavolisib in combination with Phesgo with placebo in</p>

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combination with Phesgo, as maintenance therapy, after first-line induction therapy in participants with PIK3CA-mutated, HER2-positive locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer.

1. Inavolisib plus Phesgo (experimental arm):

- Inavolisib: 9 mg tablets taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1 of maintenance treatment.
- Phesgo: administered subcutaneously every 3 weeks (Q3W) on Day 1 of each 21-day cycle

2. Placebo plus Phesgo (control arm):

- Placebo: inavolisib-matching tablets taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1 of maintenance treatment
- Phesgo: administered subcutaneously Q3W on Day 1 of each 21-day cycle

The following stratification factors will be applied:

- De novo HER2-positive metastatic disease versus recurrent disease
- Hormone receptor (HR)-positive versus HR-negative tumor status
- Overall response (OR) during induction therapy: PR/CR versus SD (non-CR/non-PD for participants with non-measurable disease)

Participants will receive maintenance therapy until PD, unacceptable toxicity, withdrawal of consent, death, or predefined study end, whichever occurs first.

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	<p>World over, 230 participants with PIK3CA-mutated, HER2-positive ABC who have not received prior systemic therapy for their disease other than the induction treatment will be randomized into the maintenance therapy of this study. In Uganda only 5 will be recruited in this study</p> <p>The proposed study design is acceptable and in line with objectives.</p> <p>What is the next course of action in case the participant disease progresses (treatment failure)</p>												
<p>5.2 Use of Placebo</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="618 730 2060 1023"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>placebo</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Use</td> <td>Placebo comparator</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type of medicinal product</td> <td>IMP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Drug form</td> <td>Immediate release tablet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Unit dose strength (s)</td> <td>Inavolisib-matching 3 mg/tablet and 9 mg/tablet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dosage level(s)</td> <td>Inavolisib-matching tablet taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Placebo is acceptable since it is will be used in addition to phesgo whose one of the API is trastuzumab which is SOC in Uganda. Placebo resembles IMP (involisib) in appearance.</p>		placebo	Use	Placebo comparator	Type of medicinal product	IMP	Drug form	Immediate release tablet	Unit dose strength (s)	Inavolisib-matching 3 mg/tablet and 9 mg/tablet	Dosage level(s)	Inavolisib-matching tablet taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1
	placebo												
Use	Placebo comparator												
Type of medicinal product	IMP												
Drug form	Immediate release tablet												
Unit dose strength (s)	Inavolisib-matching 3 mg/tablet and 9 mg/tablet												
Dosage level(s)	Inavolisib-matching tablet taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1												
<p>5.3 Randomization and Blinding and unblinding</p>	<p>CT protocol section 6.3</p> <p>After initial written informed consent has been obtained, all screening procedures and assessments and the induction therapy have been completed, participants will be randomly assigned to one of two treatment arms: inavolisib plus Phesgo or placebo plus Phesgo.</p>												

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	<p>Randomization will occur in a 1:1 ratio through use of a permuted-block randomization method to ensure a balanced assignment to each treatment arm. Randomization will be stratified by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De novo HER2-positive metastatic disease versus recurrent disease. • HR-positive versus HR-negative tumor status. • Objective response (OR) after induction therapy: PR/CR versus SD (non-CR/non-PD for participants with non-measurable disease) per RECIST v.1.1. <p>Blinding</p> <p>Study site personnel and participants will be blinded to treatment assignment during the study. The Sponsor and its agents will also be blinded to treatment assignment, with the exception of individuals who require access to participant treatment assignments to fulfil their job roles during a clinical trial. Placebo will be manufactured to match inavolisib.</p> <p>Unblinding procedure</p> <p>If unblinding is necessary for a medical emergency (e.g., in the case of a serious adverse event for which participant management might be affected by knowledge of treatment assignment), the investigator will be able to break the treatment code by contacting the IxRS. The treatment code should not be broken except in emergency situations. The investigator is not required to contact the Medical Monitor prior to breaking the treatment code. However, the investigator should inform the Medical Monitor that the treatment code has been broken</p> <p>The provisions for randomisation, blinding and unblinding are acceptable.</p>
6. Study treatment	

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6.1 IMP	Protocol section 6.1 and 6.2		
		Inavolisib	Phesgo
	Use	Experimental	Experimental/comparator
	Drug form	Immediate release tablet	Vial
	Unit dose strength (s)	3 mg/tablet and 9 mg/tablet	Loading Dose (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pertuzumab: 80 mg/mL • Trastuzumab: 60 mg/mL • rHuPH20: 2,000 U/mL Maintenance Dose <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pertuzumab: 60 mg/mL • Trastuzumab: 60 mg/mL • rHuPH20: 2,000 U/mL
Dosage level(s)	9-mg tablet taken PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle, beginning on Day 1 of Cycle 1	Loading Dose (if applicable) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pertuzumab: 1200 mg/mL • Trastuzumab: 600 mg/mL • rHuPH20: 30,000 U/mL Maintenance Dose (Q3W) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pertuzumab: 600 mg/mL • Trastuzumab: 600 mg/mL • rHuPH20: 20,000 U/mL 	
<p>Only authorized staff may supply or administer IMPs.</p> <p>Phesgo will be provided in single-dose, ready-to-use glass vials and administered subcutaneously as a fixed non-weight-based dose. In the induction therapy, a loading dose (1200 mg pertuzumab, 600 mg trastuzumab, 30,000 U rHuPH20) will be administered in the first cycle. A maintenance dose (600 mg pertuzumab, 600 mg trastuzumab, and rHuPH20 SC) will be administered subcutaneously Q3W.</p>			

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	<p>If the participant misses a dose of Phesgo for any cycle and the time between doses is ≥ 6 weeks, a reloading dose of Phesgo (1200 mg pertuzumab, 600 mg trastuzumab, and 30,000 U rHuPH20) should be given.</p> <p>Inavolisib/placebo will be administered PO QD on Days 1–21 of each 21-day cycle at a starting dose of 9 mg. Inavolisib/placebo will be administered in the clinic on Day 1 of Cycle 1, and on each subsequent scheduled visit; it will be taken at home on all non-clinic visit days without regard to the timing of administration of food.</p> <p>Justification for the doses and dosage regimen is provided in section 6 of the protocol. Considered adequate.</p>
<p>6.2 Comparator</p>	<p>The comparator is Placebo plus Phesgo</p> <p>The use of Placebo plus Phesgo as comparator is permissible since Phesgo already approved for use in stringent regulatory agencies</p>
<p>6.3 Concomitant medicines</p>	<p>During the induction therapy, the investigator’s choice of taxane-based chemotherapy (i.e., docetaxel, paclitaxel, or nab-paclitaxel) will be administered.</p> <p>Allowed optional Endocrine Therapy are tamoxifen, or one of the specified third-generation AIs (anastrozole, letrozole, or exemestane), or fulvestrant, per investigator choice.</p> <p>The study also permits use of Luteinizing Hormone-Releasing Hormone Agonists in patients on endocrine therapy and Dexamethasone Mouth Rinse for prevention or treatment of stomatitis.</p>

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	<p>Participants experiencing hyperglycemia may require anti-hyperglycemic medication. The preferred first agent is metformin</p>
	<p>Docetaxel, paclitaxel or nab-paclitaxel will be provided by the Sponsor.</p>
<p>7. Safety Monitoring</p>	<p>.</p>
<p>7.1 Participant follow-up</p>	<p>CT protocol section 1.3, 4.5 and 8.3.3</p> <p>Follow-up visits will occur on days 4, 8, 15 of cycle 1, days 1 and 10 of cycles 2 and beyond, monthly up to 3 months, and three monthly thereafter. Safety follow-up will occur 30 days from the final dose. Treatment will continue until disease progression per RECIST v1.1, unacceptable toxicity, death, withdrawal of consent, or study termination by the Sponsor. The total duration of study participation for the first individual randomized can range from 1 day to 111 months, for the last individual randomized it can range from 1 day to 74 months.</p> <p>Participant follow-up is adequately described.</p>
<p>7.2 Adverse Events</p>	<p>Protocol section appendix 3</p> <p>Definitions of adverse events, serious adverse event, are provided, Additionally, assessment of causality has been provided.</p> <p>After the initial adverse event or serious adverse event report, the investigator is required to proactively follow each participant at subsequent visits or contacts. All adverse events will be followed until the event has resolved to baseline grade or better, or the event is assessed as stable by the</p>

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	<p>investigator, or the participant is lost to follow-up (as defined in Section 7.3), or the participant withdraws consent. Further information on follow-up procedures is provided in Appendix 3.</p> <p>The investigator is obligated to assess the relationship between study treatment and each occurrence of each adverse event or serious adverse event.</p> <p>The investigator will assess the severity of each adverse event reported during the study through use of the NCI CTCAE (v5.0) grading scale.</p> <p>Symptomatic left ventricular systolic dysfunction (LVSD); (also referred to as congestive heart failure [CHF]) will be assessed as “heart failure” on the basis of NCI CTCAE v5.0</p> <p>Details are considered adequate. However;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide justification for only reporting SAE until 30 days following maintenance therapy. 2. Will the SAEs reported to the sponsor beyond the reporting period (after the final dose of study treatment After initiation of study treatment or maintenance therapy) be reported to NDA as well. 3. Objective measures are not proposed for causality assessment.
<p>7.3 Discontinuation criteria for participants and stopping criteria for study</p>	<p>CT protocol section 7.2</p> <p>A participant may withdraw from the study at any time at his or her own request or may be withdrawn at any time at the discretion of the investigator for safety, behavioral, compliance, or administrative reasons.</p>

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	<p>The primary reason for discontinuation from the study should be documented on the appropriate eCRF. If a participant requests to be withdrawn from the study, this request must be documented in the source documents and signed by the investigator.</p> <p>At the time of discontinuing from the study, if possible, an early discontinuation visit should be conducted, as shown in the schedule of activities (see Section 1.3, Table 1 and Table 2). Refer to the schedule of activities for data to be collected at the time of study discontinuation and follow-up and for any further evaluations that need to be completed.</p> <p>The participant will be permanently discontinued both from the study treatment and from the study at that time.</p> <p>If a participant withdraws consent from the study, the Sponsor may retain and continue to use any data collected before withdrawal of consent. Samples collected prior to withdrawal may be analyzed, unless the participant specifically requests that the samples be destroyed (as documented in the source documents) or local laws require destruction of the samples. However, if samples have been tested prior to withdrawal, results from those tests will remain as part of the overall research data.</p> <p>If a participant withdraws from the study, the study staff may – in accordance with local regulations use a public information source (e.g., county records) to obtain information about survival status.</p> <p>Participant discontinuation is considered acceptable.</p>
<p>7.4 Data Safety Monitoring Board</p>	<p>Refer to IDMC charter page 11 section 5.2</p>

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	<p>The Independent Data Monitoring Committee (iDMC) will regularly assess unblinded safety data throughout the study. The IDMC will monitor accruing safety data from study participants approximately every 3 months in the first year and then 6 monthly until primary analysis of PFS.</p> <p>IDMC will also convene to review safety data of all the first 20 participants who will have completed one cycle of treatment within the maintenance therapy.</p> <p>There is a provision for an ad hoc iDMC meeting in the instance of a new safety concern or safety signal.</p> <p>The charter for IDMC is duly signed</p>
<p>8. End of trial</p>	<p>CT protocol section 4.4</p> <p>9.25 years (111 months)</p> <p>The end of this study is defined as the date at which the required number of deaths (109 OS events) for the statistical analysis has been observed.</p> <p>Definition of end of trial is acceptable</p>
<p>9. Biological samples used in the study</p>	<p>Fresh or archival tumor tissue samples from metastatic disease or from a primary tumor collected prior to the start of study treatment is required and will be processed for extraction of DNA and/or RNA to enable comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP) to identify mutational and/or gene expression patterns.</p> <p>In addition, tumor tissue and blood samples will be collected to enable whole genome sequencing (WGS) or whole exome sequencing (WES) to identify somatic variants that are predictive of response</p>

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	<p>to study treatment, are associated with progression to a more severe disease state, are associated with acquired resistance to study treatment, are associated with susceptibility to developing adverse events, can lead to improved adverse event monitoring or investigation, or can increase the knowledge and understanding of disease biology and drug safety.</p> <p>For this reason, blood (plasma) samples will be collected prior to the start of study treatment, at various timepoints during study treatment, and at the study discontinuation visit.</p> <p>Pharmacokinetic (PK) samples will be collected in this study to characterize the pharmacokinetics of inavolisib administered in combination with Phesgo.</p> <p>Consent will be sought from participants for storage of samples for future use.</p> <p>Also draft submitted material transfer agreement</p> <p>Considered adequate.</p>
<p>10. Statistical measures</p>	
<p>10.1 Sample size, Trial power and Level of significance used</p>	<p>Refer to the study protocol section 9.0</p> <p>A total of 230 participants will be enrolled in this study for the analysis of the primary endpoint PFS. It is based on the following assumptions: Two-sided, stratified log-rank test at the 0.05 significance level in the FAS population, randomization ratio of 1:1, 80% power, median PFS of 10 months in the placebo+Phesgo arm and 16.4 months in the inavolisib +Phesgo arm (corresponding to an HR of 0.61) after randomization, i.e., after induction therapy, Assumption of proportionality, 10% annual loss to follow-up</p>

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	<p>The sample size calculation and justification are acceptable. A power of 80% and a 95% confidence level have been considered, with a 10% adjustment for loss to follow-up.</p>
<p>10.2 Planned analyses</p>	<p>Analyses plans have been provided for each of the primary, secondary and exploratory objectives, including a description of the population and the statistical analysis tests and methods. Other analyses include summaries of demographic and baseline characteristics, pharmacokinetic analyses and immunogenicity analyses. A statistical analysis plan will be finalized with more detail.</p>
	<p>Adequate details are provided. The planned analyses reflect the study objectives.</p>
<p>10.3 Analysis sets</p>	<p>The analysis sets for this study are as follows;</p> <p>Full analyses set: All randomized participants: participants will be included in the analyses according to the treatment to which they were assigned.</p> <p>Response-evaluable population: All participants with measurable disease at baseline per the investigator according to RECIST v1.1.</p> <p>Responders: All participants with a response for the analysis of the duration of response</p> <p>Safety-evaluable population: All participants exposed to study treatment; participants will be analyzed according to the treatment that they actually received.</p>

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	PK-evaluable population: All participants who received any dose of study medication and who have at least one post-baseline PK sample available
	Adequate details have been provided. The analysis sets reflect the trial's objectives and end-points.
10.4 Interim analysis	Study protocol section 9.4 There will be an interim OS analysis at the time of the primary PFS analysis, and a final OS analysis. The critical value at the final analysis will be adjusted accordingly to maintain the 5% overall type I error rate, per standard Lan-DeMets methodology. In addition, DSMB will meet every 3 months to discuss safety of participants and data accrued.
	The charter is duly signed
11. Risk-Benefit Analysis	
11.1 General risk-benefit assessment	Refer to the appendix 4 in study protocol page 159 which has extensively discussed Management of Identified and Potential Risks.
	The risk mitigation strategy provided is considered adequate
	Refer to section 4.3.6 of the IB.

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11.2 Risk to the embryo and/or foetus	<p>Inavolisib was well-tolerated up to 6 mg/kg/day when administered PO QD on gestation day (GD) 7 through 17, with maternal findings limited to non-adverse lower body weight gain and transient glucose increases at \square2 mg/kg/day.</p> <p>Inavolisib-related effects on embryo-fetal development at 2 mg/kg/day included adverse decreases in fetal body weight and placental weight, and at 6 mg/kg/day higher post implantation loss, lower fetal viability, and teratogenicity. The most frequent findings of fetal external, visceral, and skeletal malformations were edema, anasarca, absent eye bulge, microphthalmia, fused thoracic arch, and kyphosis of the vertebral column. The no observable effect level (NOAEL) for maternal toxicity is considered to be 6 mg/kg/day (the highest dose tested).</p> <p>Protocol has excluded pregnant women and has also emphasised participants to use contraception</p>
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NON-CLINICAL ASSESSMENT

Issue	Workspace
1. Introduction	<p>The nonclinical testing strategy provides a comprehensive assessment of efficacy, pharmacology, and safety that supports the evaluation of inavolisib in clinical trials as a potential therapeutic for locally advanced or metastatic, PIK3CA-mutated solid tumors. Inavolisib as a single agent, or inavolisib in combination with other anti-cancer therapies, is being developed by Roche for the treatment of locally advanced or metastatic PIK3CA-mutated solid tumors, including breast cancer. The non-clinical information is provided in the investigator's brochure.</p>
2. Pharmacology	
2.1 Primary pharmacodynamics	<p>Refer inavolisib IB section 4.1.2</p> <p>Invitro studies</p> <p>PI3K Isoform Biochemical Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1792) In a biochemical assay, inavolisib was shown to be a potent inhibitor of PI3Kα. Inavolisib is 2676-fold more potent against PI3Kα than PI3Kβ, 337-fold more potent against PI3Kα than PI3Kδ, and 574-fold more potent against PI3Kα than on PI3Kγ</p> <p>Kinase Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1794) Inavolisib was tested in the Invitrogen kinase panel and found to have high specificity for PI3K. Inavolisib inhibited 3 of 224 kinases in the Invitrogen kinase panel at > 80% at 1 μM. Two of the kinases, PI3Kα and PI3Kγ, are targets of inavolisib. Additionally, inavolisib inhibited PI3KC2β, a PI3K family member, at 82%. Inavolisib was > 2000-fold less selective for all other kinases tested relative to PI3Kα</p> <p>Mutant Selectivity of Inavolisib (Study 16-1793) Inavolisib is a potent PI3K inhibitor in SW48 cells and demonstrated a stronger effect in SW48 lines that were engineered to harbor a <i>PIK3CA</i> mutation (see Table 3). When assayed by the</p>

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pPRAS40 assay, inavolisib was 2.4-fold more potent in E545K cells and 2.6-fold more potent in H1047R cells relative to the *PIK3CA*-WT parental cells. The treatment of cells with inavolisib leads to depletion of p110 α protein in the HCC1954 HER2+ cell line that contains the hotspot H1047R *PIK3CA* mutation. Inavolisib did not change the p110 α protein level in the HDQ-P1 cell line that is WT for *PIK3CA*.

Inavolisib Activity in HER2+ Breast Cancer Cells

Inavolisib-induced mutant p110 α degradation is enhanced by receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) activity and provides benefit in HER2+ p110 α -mutated cancers. To further understand whether inhibitor-induced mutant p110 α degradation is dependent on its recruitment to activated RTKs, the efficacy of two clinically relevant molecules, inavolisib (an inducer of mutant p110 α degradation) and BYL719 (also known as alpelisib, an inhibitor but not degrader of mutant p110 α), was investigated. The results showed a significant difference between the sensitivity to inavolisib and BYL719 in HER2-amplified (~20-fold difference between the mean IC50 values) versus HER2-negative cell lines (6-fold difference between two inhibitors). Both inhibitors were not differentiated in *PIK3CA*-WT cell lines regardless of *HER2* status (Figure 3). These data implied that RTK activity may define the sensitivity of cell lines to inhibitors inducing degradation of mutant p110 α .

In vivo studies

Single Agent Efficacy and Pharmacodynamics

Nonclinical studies were conducted to determine whether PO QD dosing of inavolisib as a single agent in vivo is efficacious against orthotopic (mammary fat pad) human KPL-4 (13-3399 L) or HCC1954x1 (13-3399 O) breast cancer xenografts in immunodeficient mice. In both studies, dose-dependent TGI was observed, with the highest TGI noted at the MTD.

In all single-agent efficacy studies, tolerability of PO QD administration of inavolisib was assessed by percent change in body weight during the course of the study.

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	<p>In Study 13-3399 L, all doses were tolerated. For Study 13-3399 O, all doses were well tolerated with the exception of 50 mg/kg. In the 50-mg/kg dose group, 1 mouse was euthanized on Day 6 as a result of > 20% body weight loss, and another mouse exhibited 15% body weight loss on Day 6 but recovered for the remainder of the dosing period. The remaining 8 mice experienced < 10% body weight loss during the study.</p> <p>Efficacy of Inavolisib in Combination with Standard-of-Care Therapies Inavolisib combined with the HER2-targeted antibodies trastuzumab and pertuzumab was investigated in the KPL-4 <i>PIK3CA</i>-mutated HER2+ breast cancer xenograft model (18-1388 J). Mice were treated with inavolisib at 25 mg/kg PO QD for 28 days, trastuzumab (3 mg/kg) plus pertuzumab (2.5 mg/kg) IV QW×4 or the combination. Treatment with single agent inavolisib resulted in 134% TGI and treatment with trastuzumab plus pertuzumab 134% TGI. The combination of inavolisib plus trastuzumab and pertuzumab resulted in 148% TGI (Figure 8). Inavolisib was also combined with the HER2-targeted antibody-drug conjugate T-DM1 in the KPL-4 model. Mice treated with inavolisib at 25 mg/kg PO QDx21 showed 122% TGI, while treatment of mice with 3 mg/kg T-DM1 IV single dose resulted in 177% TGI. The combination of inavolisib with T-DM1 was more efficacious than single agents, resulting in TGI of 232%</p> <p>Details of primary pharmacodynamics are considered acceptable. They support use of the drug in the study population and with the standard of care.</p>
<p>2.2 Secondary pharmacodynamics</p>	<p>In Vitro Studies In Vitro Pharmacology Receptor and Enzyme Selectivity Assay (Studies 15-0292 and 15-1941) No significant off-target responses were observed when inavolisib was evaluated in radioligand binding and enzyme assays including major classes of biogenic amine receptors, neuropeptide receptors, ion channels, neurotransmitter transporters, and enzymes.</p>

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	Secondary PD studies did not reveal any significant off target effects.
2.3 Safety pharmacology	<p>Refer to IB section 4.3.8</p> <p>Inavolisib does not show significant inhibition of cardiac human ether-à-go-go-related gene (hERG), sodium, or calcium channels in vitro (15-3355, 15-0486, 15-0487) at clinically relevant concentrations.</p> <p>In the single-dose cardiovascular safety pharmacology study in dogs (15-3293), inavolisib-related cardiovascular effects included generally dose-dependent, reversible, and non-adverse decreases in heart rate, increases in arterial pressure and contractility, lengthening of PR and QT intervals.</p> <p>No cardiovascular findings were observed in the GLP 1- and 3-month repeat-dose toxicity study in dogs using external ECG and blood pressure measurements (15-3288, 18-2455). The inavolisib exposures were comparable in the telemetry and repeat-dose dog studies. No neurological effects were observed in the functional observation battery (FOB) assessment in rats up to 10 mg/kg (15-3303), or in neurological examinations in dogs up to 1.5 mg/kg (15-3288). No effects on respiratory rate were observed up to 1.5 mg/kg in dogs (15-3288, 18-2455).</p>
	No significant concerns were identified in safety pharmacology
2.4 Pharmacodynamic drug interactions	<p>Refer to IB section 4.1.4</p> <p>No Pharmacodynamic Drug Interactions studies have been conducted.</p>
	Not provided
3. Pharmacokinetics	
3.1 Methods of PK analysis	<p>IB section 4.2</p> <p>A series of in vitro and in vivo studies were completed to characterize exposure in nonclinical species used in efficacy and toxicology studies. In vivo PK studies of inavolisib were performed in mice, rats, dogs, and cynomolgus monkeys. Inavolisib protein binding was determined in mouse,</p>

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	<p>rat, rabbit, dog, cynomolgus monkey, and human pooled plasma, human serum albumin, and human AAG. Metabolites of inavolisib were identified in liver microsomes from rat, dog, and human.</p> <p>Additional in vitro studies were conducted to assess the potential of inavolisib for DDI. Toxicokinetic (TK) evaluations were performed in association with toxicology studies in rats and dogs as part of the Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) and non-GLP toxicity studies. The results from these studies provided information on the nonclinical pharmacokinetics of inavolisib to aid in the selection of the appropriate species for toxicology testing and to enable selection of an appropriate starting dose in human clinical trials.</p>
<p>3.2 Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion</p>	<p>Relevant guidelines have been followed and justification of choice of animals has been provided.</p> <p>Absorption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioavailability (F) of inavolisib following PO administration ranged from 57.5% in monkeys to 100% in mice (14-3676, 15-0063, 15-3384, 15-0630) and the fraction absorbed ranged from approximately 45% to 50% in rats (17-2251). Terminal half-life (t_{1/2}) ranged from 0.72 to 4.75 hours across preclinical species. • Inavolisib had low-to-moderate plasma CL in mice, monkeys and dogs and high plasma CL in rats, relative to hepatic blood flow (Davies et al. 1993), and a moderate volume of distribution relative to total body water across all nonclinical species (14-3676, 15-0785, 16-0165, and 15-0630). • The TK of inavolisib was evaluated in rats and dogs. In general, exposures increased dose proportionally and were similar on Day 1 and after multiple administrations in the 4-week and 13-week studies. In rats, exposure was generally approximately 2-fold higher in females than in males while there were no sex-related differences in exposure in dogs <p>Distribution</p>

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Plasma protein binding of inavolisib ranged from 27% to 75% bound (mouse, 75%; rat, 40%; rabbit, 47%; dog, 31%; monkey, 27%; and human, 37%) and did not appear to be concentration dependent over the concentration range tested (0.1–10 μ M). The mean binding of inavolisib to 1 mg/mL of human AAG and 40 mg/mL human serum albumin was approximately 22% and 26%, respectively, across the same concentration range (15-3820). Mean blood-plasma concentration ratio ranged from 0.75 to 0.84 in rats.

Inavolisib-related radioactivity was extensively distributed in rat tissues and organs. By 672 hours postdose, levels of radioactivity in all tissues were below quantifiable levels except in the adrenal gland, medulla and cortex and uveal tract, where concentrations remained quantifiable until 1344 hours postdose. Concentrations in the CNS tissues were low or lower than the limit of quantitation for the entire duration of the study

Metabolism

In Vitro Metabolism

Inavolisib was relatively stable in rat, dog and human liver microsomes (HLM), with more than 99% recovered in all incubations as parent compound. Three minor metabolites were detected. M1 was an oxidative metabolite (+16 amu), M2 resulted from the oxidation and opening of the oxazolidinone ring (+32 amu), and M3 was a dealkylated and oxidated metabolite (–55 amu). No human-specific metabolites were detected in liver microsomes (16-0871). Formation of the minor ring-opened oxidative metabolite M2 was principally mediated by CYP3A4 and CYP3A5 (16-1673).

In Vivo Metabolism

Following a single oral dose of radio-labeled [14 C] inavolisib in rats, inavolisib was the most abundant drug-related material in plasma (80.6% of the total drug-related exposure) and circulating metabolites were M5 (imidazole ring cleavage) and M27 (–29 amu), which accounted for 7.3% and 3.6% of the total drug-related exposure, respectively (18-0814).

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	<p>Inavolisib was the most abundant drug-related material in urine (21.9% of the administered dose), feces (31.9% of the dose) and bile (3.7% of the dose). In urine, M5 accounted for an average of 2.5% of the dose. In feces, M20 (N-dealkylation and oxidation) and M5 were not separable in male rats and together accounted for 7% of the dose, while M20 and M5 accounted for 2.2% and 5.2% of dose in female rats, respectively. In bile, M5 accounted for an average of 1.6% of the dose.</p> <p>Overall, metabolism of inavolisib in rats was primarily through oxidation, glucuronidation and imidazole ring cleavage</p> <p>Excretion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mean total recovery of radioactivity after a single oral dose of [14C] inavolisib in rats was 91.9% of the administered dose. The primary route of elimination of radioactivity in rats was the feces, where 57%-63% of the administered dose was recovered, while elimination in urine accounted for 23% to 35% of the dose. Biliary excretion accounted for approximately 9% to 15% of the dose (17-2251). • Renal CL accounted for approximately 30% of plasma CL in monkeys and dogs
<p>3.3 Pharmacokinetic drug interactions (enzymes, transporter, other)</p>	<p>Details provided are satisfactory i.e 3 minor metabolites identified, no human-specific metabolites were detected in liver microsomes</p> <p>In vitro studies indicated that inavolisib was not a potent reversible inhibitor ($IC_{50} > 50 \mu M$) of any of the CYPs evaluated (CYP1A2, CYP2B6, CYP2C8, CYP2C9, CYP2C19, CYP2D6, and CYP3A; 15-2967) while displaying mild metabolism-dependent inhibition of CYP3A with extrapolated maximal inactivation ($kinact$) and concentration at 50% $kinact$ (KI) values of $0.077 \pm 0.006 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $88 \pm 10 \mu M$, respectively (16-0806).</p> <p>Inavolisib was not a metabolism-dependent inhibitor of CYP1A2, CYP2B6, CYP2C8, CYP2C9, CYP2C19, or CYP2D6 enzyme activity. These results suggest a low likelihood of CYP inhibition by inavolisib at clinically relevant concentrations.</p>

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	<p>Inavolisib appeared to have the potential to weakly induce CYP3A4 (16-0131). Following incubation with 1 μM of inavolisib, the mean percent activity of CYP3A4/5 compared with the vehicle control increased up to 4-fold (4.05-fold \pm 0.55). At this concentration, the level of enzyme induction was < 21% of the positive control rifampicin at 10 μM.</p> <p>In vitro studies (19-1182) showed that inavolisib was a substrate of P-glycoprotein (P-gp) and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP), but not a substrate of OATP1B1, OATP1B3, OCT1, OCT2, OAT1, OAT2, MATE1, and MATE2K. These results suggest that absorption and/or systemic exposure may be affected by inhibitors of P-gp or BCRP. Inavolisib is unlikely to be a victim of transporter-related DDIs for the other transporters tested.</p> <p>In vitro studies investigating the potential of inavolisib to inhibit drug transporters are summarized in Table 5 (18-2263). Based on these in vitro results and considering the guidance documents on DDI from the FDA and the EMA (EMA Guideline on the investigation of drug interactions 2012 and FDA Guidance for industry 2012 and 2017), inavolisib does not appear to have the potential to inhibit any of the transporters tested at clinically relevant concentrations.</p>
	<p>PK drug interaction clearly described</p>
<p>3.4 Other pharmacokinetic studies (e.g PK of metabolite, novel excipients, genomic integration and inadvertent germline transmission of gene transfer vectors)</p>	<p>Not provided</p>
<p>4. Toxicology</p>	<p>Not provided</p>

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4.1 Animal species selection/study design

The nonclinical safety of inavolisib has been assessed in a comprehensive battery of toxicology studies which include single-dose and repeat-dose general toxicology studies (once a day [QD] PO dosing) of up to 3 months' duration in rats and dogs; in vitro and in vivo genetic toxicology studies; in vitro phototoxicity study; in vitro and in vivo secondary pharmacology and safety pharmacology studies; and embryofetal development (Segment II) studies in rats. In addition, RO7533297 (M5), which was initially identified as a degradant in the drug product, has been assessed in the in vitro bacterial reverse mutation assay.

The pivotal toxicology and safety pharmacology studies intended to support human clinical trials were conducted in accordance with U.S. Food and Drug Administration GLP regulations (21 CFR Part 58) or Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) principles of GLP [C(97)186/Final] and were conducted in a country that is a member of the OECD Mutual Acceptance of Data Program. Additional supportive toxicological, pharmacological, and PK studies were carried out as scientifically carefully conducted non-GLP studies.

The Sprague-Dawley rats and Beagle dogs were selected as appropriate species for in vivo nonclinical safety evaluations on the basis of high protein homology, the demonstration of in vivo PD, adequate in vivo exposure and comparable in vitro metabolic profile to humans. The sequence homology of p110 α is very high for both rat and dog when compared with humans, with the overall homology being 98.7% and 99.8%, respectively. The amino acid residues surrounding the binding site are 100% identical for all 3 species. All major metabolites observed in vitro using HLMs were also detected in rat and dog liver microsomes, and no human-specific metabolites were identified and there were sufficient exposures of parent drug for toxicology evaluations (Section 4.2). In addition, both rats and dogs demonstrated in vivo PD (e.g., hyperglycemia) of PI3K inhibition at exposures similar to that of 9 mg in the clinic (Section 4.3.3), suggesting both rats and dogs are pharmacologically relevant species for the safety assessment of inavolisib.

Details are satisfactory: rats and dogs were the animal species which show similar PD and PK like humans. Relevant guidelines were also followed.

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<p>4.2 Single dose toxicity</p>	<p>Refer to IB section 4.3.2</p> <p>In a single dose oral tolerability and TK study in male Sprague-Dawley rats (15-0896), inavolisib was well tolerated, with treatment-related findings limited to dose-dependent body weight loss (up to 9% at 30 mg/kg) and transient increase in glucose (mild-to-moderate increase at multiple timepoints at 15 and 30 mg/kg). Therefore, the MTD of inavolisib in rats after a single dose was determined to be 30 mg/kg, the highest dose tested.</p> <p>In the single-dose oral tolerability and TK studies in Beagle dogs (15-1140, 15-2688), inavolisib-related findings were limited to ≥ 3 mg/kg and included dose-related body weight loss (up to 6% at 10 mg/kg) and clinical pathology findings of markedly increased postdose glucose concentrations and inflammation. The increased postdose glucose returned to baseline at 24 hours in 3 mg/kg animals but not in 10-mg/kg animals. Therefore, the MTD of inavolisib in dogs after a single dose was determined to be 10 mg/kg.</p> <p>Details clearly provided including the maximum tolerated doses of the two animal species dogs and rats. Some toxicities were identified. These are addressed in the study risk management plan.</p>
<p>4.3 Repeat-dose toxicity</p>	<p>Repeat-dose, general toxicology studies (QD PO dosing) conducted in rats and dogs ranged from 1 week to 3 months (see Table 6).</p> <p>The dose limiting toxicities (DLTs) identified in nonclinical toxicology studies were consistent with the anticipated pharmacologic effects of PI3K inhibition, and included hyperglycemia and body weight loss in rats and dogs, and inflammation in dogs. In addition, bone marrow hypocellularity, atrophy of glandular and reproductive tissues and eye lens degeneration were observed in the rats; and lymphoid depletion and swelling of the lens fibers in the eye were observed in the dogs. Findings were generally dose-dependent and reversible, and considered to be clinically monitorable and/or manageable. The lens fiber degeneration observed in some rats at 10 mg/kg (at least 3.9x the AUC exposure of 985 ng • hr/mL at 9 mg in the clinic, using the more conservative estimation based on lower exposure in male rats) was considered irreversible.</p>

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	Some toxicities as listed above were identified. These have been considered in the study risk management plan.
4.4 Genotoxicity	<p>Refer to IB section 4.3.4 Inavolisib: Bacterial Reverse Mutation Assay (Studies 15-3356 and 16-1286)</p> <p>Inavolisib was considered not mutagenic in <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> strains (TA98, TA100, TA1535 and TA1537) or <i>Escherichia coli</i> (WP2 uvrA) in the absence or presence of an exogenous metabolic activation system (S-9).</p> <p>In the first study, inavolisib showed equivocal/weak positive increase of revertant numbers of strain TA98 in the presence of S-9 (2.1-fold and 1.9-fold in 2 separate assays, respectively) (Study 15-3356). A further study was done in strain TA98 in the presence of S-9 only, using 2 lots of inavolisib (Lots G02967907.1-20 [original lot, purity 98%] and 60470-32 [purified lot, purity 100%]), employing both plate incorporation and preincubation methodologies (Study 16-1286). No increase in revertant numbers \geq 2-fold the concurrent vehicle control was observed using either the plate incorporation or preincubation method for either lot of inavolisib. Therefore, the weak signal observed in Study 15-3356 was not reproducible upon further testing. Additional testing was not considered necessary in accordance with ICH-S2(R1) (DHHS et al. 2012b).</p>
	No significant issues noted.
4.5 Carcinogenicity	<p>No carcinogenicity studies with inavolisib have been conducted. No carcinogenicity studies are currently planned because such studies are not required for drugs intended for advanced cancer patients per ICH-S9 (DHHS et al. 2010).</p>
	N/A
4.6 Reproductive and developmental toxicity	Refer to IB section 4.3.6

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	<p>Microscopic changes indicative of potential effects on fertility in males and females were observed in the 1- and 3-month general toxicity studies (see Section 4.3.3). In a GLP enhanced preliminary embryo-fetal development study in female Sprague Dawley (SD) rats (19-0593), inavolisib was well-tolerated up to 6 mg/kg/day when administered PO QD on gestation day (GD) 7 through 17, with maternal findings limited to non-adverse lower body weight gain and transient glucose increases at ≥ 2 mg/kg/day.</p> <p>Inavolisib-related effects on embryo-fetal development at 2 mg/kg/day included adverse decreases in fetal body weight and placental weight, and at 6 mg/kg/day higher post-implantation loss, lower fetal viability, and teratogenicity. The most frequent findings of fetal external, visceral, and skeletal malformations were edema, anasarca, absent eye bulge, microphthalmia, fused thoracic arch, and kyphosis of the vertebral column. The no observable effect level (NOAEL) for maternal toxicity is considered to be 6 mg/kg/day (the highest dose tested). The NOEL and NOAEL for embryo-fetal development is considered to be 0.6 mg/kg/day, corresponding to maternal plasma exposure levels of 46.3 ng/mL and 256 ng·h/mL for C_{max} and AUC₀₋₂₄, respectively, on GD 17. This is ~0.26x the AUC exposure of 985 ng • hr/mL at 9 mg in the clinic (Study GO39374).</p> <p>These findings warrant the continued use of highly effective contraception in clinical trials utilizing inavolisib.</p> <p>Since embryo lethality and teratogenicity have been observed in rats in the enhanced preliminary embryo-fetal development study, a definitive study in rats or a confirmatory study in a second species is not warranted.</p>
	<p>The use of contraceptives while on this study is highly recommended.</p>
	<p>Juvenile toxicity studies were not done.</p>

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4.6.1 Juvenile toxicity studies	Study population excludes the juvenile population
4.6.2 Other studies (including enhanced PPND studies)	Not provided
	No other studies were provided in the IB
4.6.3 Recommendations for contraception measures	The IB recommends the use of highly effective contraception in clinical trials utilizing inavolisib.
	Provisions for contraceptive measures are stated in the protocol.
4.7 Local tolerance	No studies done.
	NO information provided on local tolerance applicant justified that the intended route of administration of inavolisib to patients is PO, and no dedicated local tolerance studies have been conducted
4.8 Other toxicity studies	Not provided
	No other information is provided
5. Additional considerations	
5.1 First-in-human trials	Not applicable since this is a phase 3 study.

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5.2 GLP aspects	<p>The pivotal toxicology and safety pharmacology studies intended to support human clinical trials were conducted in accordance with U.S. Food and Drug Administration GLP regulations (21 CFR Part 58). The studies were also conducted in a country that is a member of the OECD Mutual Acceptance of Data Program.</p> <p>Considered acceptable.</p>
6. Assessor's overall conclusions on the non-clinical part	<p>The non-clinical assessment demonstrates that the IMP is efficacious however some toxicities were identified. These should be addressed in the risk management plan.</p>

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QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Issue	Workspace and Evaluator's comment
1. GMP Compliance	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Information about all manufacturers involved (drug substance, drug product, placebo, etc) and evidence of GMP (manufacturing licenses/ GMP certificates/any other evidence of GMP compliance):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the site • Function • Confirmation of a valid license <p>F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd</p> <p>Grenzacherstrasse 124</p> <p>CH-4070 Basel, Switzerland</p> <p>GMP certificates seen</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>GMP information submitted is adequate</p>
2. Drug Substance (S)	

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<p>2.1 Drug Substance</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>For registered, non-modified product, has the SmPC been provided?</p> <p>For new unregistered products, does the active substance have a monograph or belong to an authorised drug product registered by NDA or a stringent regulatory body? (If NO fill in the full S section)</p> <p>This product is not in a Monograph</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>The products have not yet received market authorization in Uganda (unregistered products)</p> <p>This is a novel product not yet registered in any stringent regulatory agency at the time of application</p>
<p>2.2 Nomenclature and structure.</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Has the Chemical structure, Chemical name and other names or codes been provided?</p> <p>For biologicals, has the description of the predicted structure been provided?</p> <p>Refer to S.1.2 of the IMPD (2S)-2-[[2-[(4S)-4-(Difluoromethyl)-2-oxo-3-oxazolidinyl]-5,6 dihydroimidazo[1,2-d][1,4]be</p> <p>Inavolisib (NIN): RO7113755, GDC-0077, and G02967907</p> <p>The structural formular has been provided</p>

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	<p>Comment</p> <p>Does the submitted documentation cover this subsection adequately?</p> <p>Applicant provided the nomenclature and structure which conform to the similar molecule on PUBCHEM. This molecule(compound) of involisib exhibits 2 chiral centres hence 4 isomers are expected which can affect safe and efficacy.</p>
2.3 General properties	<p>Workspace</p> <p>For chemicals, have the physicochemical properties likely to affect pharmacological or toxicological safety, eg solubility, pKa, been mentioned?</p> <p>For biologicals, has the proposed mechanism of action been mentioned?</p> <p>Refer to S.1.3</p> <p>Applicant has provided physiochemical properties including solubility, melting point and hygroscopicity.</p> <p>The compound is soluble in the following solvents below Ethanol</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Methanol2. Tetrahydrofuran3. Ethyl Acetate4. Methyl Isobutyl Ketone <p>PKa =3.3, melting point 212°C–216°C and hygroscopicity is < 0.3% at 90% relative humidity</p>

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	<p>Comment</p> <p>Does the submitted documentation cover this subsection adequately?</p> <p>Class 2 and 3 solvents has been provided no class 1 solvents used.</p>
<p>2.4 Manufacture (Applicable to new products)</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>For chemical IMPs, comment on the process including critical steps and process controls, stereochemistry of the starting materials, solvents, metal catalysts, and critical reagents.</p> <p>Refer to Figure S.2.2-1 for the RO7113755 Synthetic Scheme.</p> <p>RO7113755 manufactured in 3 GMP steps below</p> <p>Step 1</p> <p>A reactor was charged with RO7194474, RO7194473, cesium carbonate, copper(II) acetate, trans-N,N'-dimethylcyclohexane-1,2-diamine, and 2-methyltetrahydrofuran (2-MeTHF). The mixture was heated until the desired reaction conversion was achieved. An aqueous treatment with aqueous sodium hydrogen sulfate solution was performed, followed by removal of the precipitated solids by filtration. Following phase separation, the organic phase was further washed with water, and then the solvent 2-MeTHF was switched to acetonitrile. Water was added to afford a slurry that was isolated, washed with acetonitrile/water, and dried under reduced pressure to provide RO7194336.</p> <p>Step 2</p> <p>A reactor was charged with RO7194336, RO0118275, tribasic potassium phosphate, copper (I) oxide, and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The mixture was heated under an inert atmosphere until the</p>

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	<p>desired reaction conversion was achieved. Water and dichloromethane (DCM) were added, and layers were separated. The aqueous layer was washed with DCM. 2-MeTHF and an aqueous solution of sodium hydrogen sulfate/sodium chloride were added. The aqueous layer was removed, and the organic layer was further washed with aqueous sodium chloride. The resulting 2-MeTHF solution was treated with SiliaMetS □ dimercaptotriazine (a silica-supported copper scavenger) and the solid removed by filtration to give a clear solution of the Step 2a intermediate. In Step 2b, the ammonium salt is formed by addition of ammonium in methanol, and the mixture is distilled to a reduced volume. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was added and the mixture cooled. The isolated product wet cake was washed with THF and dried under reduced pressure to provide the ammonium salt RO7304380-001.</p> <p>Step 3</p> <p>A reactor was charged with RO7304380-001, N-hydroxysuccinimide, and THF. The mixture was cooled, and then ammonia solution in isopropanol, and EDC-HCl, as a suspension in THF, were added sequentially. Upon the desired reaction conversion and aqueous workups with aqueous sodium chloride and ammonium hydroxide/sodium chloride solutions, the organic phase was polish filtered. Ethanol was added, followed by seed crystals of RO7113755. THF was solvent-switched to ethanol, and then ethanol/water was added and the mixture cooled to 20□C□25□C. The resulting slurry was isolated, washed with ethanol/water, and dried under reduced pressure, with agitation, to provide RO7113755.</p>
	<p>Comment</p>

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	<p>Are the production sites clearly identified?</p> <p>Substance: are the manufacturing processes and their controls adequately described?</p> <p>Class 2 and 3 were the solvents used in the manufacture of this compound.</p> <p>No alert structures are present</p>
<p>2.5 Control of Materials, critical steps and intermediates.</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Has the information on critical materials and their control been provided?</p> <p>For biological IMPs, has the source [materials], history of generation of cell substrate, the cell bank system, characterization and testing, and cell substrate stability and/or summary of source, history and generation of virus seed material been provided?</p> <p>If applicable, has the summary of compendial and non-compendial raw materials or materials of human origin been mentioned?</p> <p>Refer to S.2.3 of the IMPD</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the control of materials, critical steps and intermediates adequately described?</p> <p>Applicant provided control of materials</p> <p>Provided information on specification for example the appearance, colour, identity (IR &HPLC), purity, organic impurities and residual solvents.</p>

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	<p>this information is considered adequate</p>
<p>2.6 Process validation and/or evaluation</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are copies of the validation reports submitted?</p> <p>Refer to section S.2.5 of the IMPD</p> <p>The current RO7113755 drug substance manufacturing process involves neither aseptic processes nor sterilization processes. Therefore, no information is provided.</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Is the process validation adequately described?</p> <p>The justification provided is acceptable.</p>
<p>2.7 Manufacturing process development</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are there significant differences from the manufacturing process of toxicological or previous clinical batches?</p> <p>Refer to section S.2.6 of IMPD</p> <p>The significant process changes are summarized in this section as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For toxicological studies, the first batch of RO7113755 (GDC-0077, Batch G02967907.1-20) was produced at Genentech (SSF) as shown in Figure S.2.6-1 • The first GMP batch of RO7113755 was prepared according to Figure S.2.6-2. This process required a salt break and salt reformation step (Step 4) for purity improvement.

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- Further process optimization resulted in the manufacturing process depicted in Figure S.2.6-3, in which the following changes were implemented:

1. In step 2, the copper (I) oxide was charged to the hot mixture to improve the robustness of the reaction. As part of the workup, the tetrahydrofuran (THF) solution of RO7304380 was treated with a silica-based metal scavenger (SiliaMetS® dimercaptotriazine) to control the level of residual copper.
2. The previous step 4 salt break and salt reformation step was removed due to the improved impurity profile of the isolated ammonium salt RO7304380-001 isolated in step 3.
3. In the final step (step 4), the amide bond formation was performed using N-hydroxysuccinimide and N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride instead of 1,1'-carbonyldiimidazole. The intermediate ammonium salt RO7304380-001 was used directly without breaking the salt to form the corresponding acid, as was performed in the previous process described above.

Further process development and manufacturing was performed at Roche (Basel). The current manufacturing process is described in Section S.2.2 *Description of Manufacturing Process and Process Controls*. The step numbering has been modified such that the former Steps 2 and 3 are now described as Steps 2a and 2b, and the final step is now Step 3. The current manufacturing route implemented the following changes (refer to Figure S.2.2-1 in

Description of Manufacturing Process and Process Controls).

1. In step 2, the copper (I) oxide catalyst was added with the other solids prior to heating for operational simplicity and to minimize possible exposure to air. Either mode of catalyst addition is acceptable, and

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	<p>dictated by technical/facility capabilities, as long as strict exclusion of air (oxygen) from the process is maintained.</p> <p>2. The process solvent in Step 2 workup was changed from THF to 2-methyltetrahydrofuran (2-MeTHF) to aid in further processing and improve water removal efficiency in distillation. THF is still used in the isolation of the Step 2 product.</p> <p>3. Step 2 aqueous workup was performed with NaHSO₄/NaCl mixture to fully dissolve salts to aid phase separations.</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Is the manufacturing process development adequately described?</p> <p><i>Applicant has adequately described the manufacturing process</i></p>
<p>2.8 Characterisation, Elucidation of the structure and other characteristics</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are the methods used to characterize the product mentioned?</p> <p>Is the confirmed structure of the drug substance based on synthetic route and spectral analysis?</p> <p>Refer to section S.3.1 of the IMPD for the elucidation of structure and other characteristics [RO7113755].</p> <p>The structure of RO7113755 (GDC-0077) drug substance has been established by multiple analytical techniques. The following analyses were performed to elucidate the structure of RO7113755:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy- The ¹H and ¹³C spectra exhibit the chemical shifts and the corresponding internuclear couplings expected for the molecular structure. • Infrared (IR) spectroscopy -The presence of the principal functional groups of the molecule is supported by observation of their characteristic vibrational frequencies in the IR spectrum. • Ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy - The UV spectrum shows the characteristics expected of the chromophores present in the structure. • Mass spectroscopy - The mass spectrum shows an ([M+H]) signal that is consistent with the mass of the compound. • X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) • X-ray crystallography
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Is the drug substance sufficiently characterised?</p> <p>The structure of the drug substance has been adequately characterised.</p>
<p>2.9 Impurities</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>For chemical IMPs: does it comply with a Pharmacopeia and if so, with which one (US, EU, JP, other)?</p> <p>Are the impurities from the degradation products, potential genotoxic impurities of solvents and catalysts (if applicable), residual solvents used for the purification of small molecules, and any control issues mentioned?</p>

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	<p>Refer to section S.3.2 of the IMPD</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Are impurities sufficiently characterised?</p> <p>7 potential organic impurities have been provided by the applicant.</p> <p>No degradation related to drug substance impurities were observed in stability studies. No genotoxic impurities were identified using DEREK Nexus and Leadscope Model Applier.</p> <p>Only class 2 and 3 solvents were used.</p> <p>Inorganic impurities were Copper(II) acetate and Copper(I) oxide which were controlled as per ICH guideline Q3D.</p> <p>Impurities have been characterised</p>
<p>2.10 Control of the drug substance (Specifications)</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>For substances not controlled by a pharmacopeial monograph, are the proposed specifications, test methods and limits well indicated?</p> <p>The specifications are indicated. Refer to S.4.1 of the IMPD</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Are the specifications proposed for the drug substance with the appropriate limits?</p> <p>The specifications are all within limits.</p>

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<p>2.11 Analytical Procedures</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is an in-house analytical method used?</p> <p>If a monograph standard is used and the method is not that specified in the monograph, is there an equivalent of the test method?</p> <p>Both compendial and Non compendial analytical procedures were used to control RO7113755</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Are the analytical methods adequately described?</p> <p>The methods have been adequately described.</p>
<p>2.12 Validation of analytical procedures</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are copies of the validation reports for critical analytical procedures used for control of the substance?</p> <p>Copies of validation results have been submitted for the products.</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the process validation adequately described?</p> <p>Process validation has been adequately described</p>
<p>2.13 Batch analyses</p>	<p>Workspace</p>

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	<p>Do the results or range of results state if the substance complies with the proposed specifications?</p> <p>All the results met the acceptable criteria</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the data for representative batch analyses provided for all the relevant manufacturing process and for each drug substance manufacturer?</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>2.14 Justification of the specifications</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the drug substance specification justified with the critical specifications stated and acceptance criteria given?</p> <p>Refer to section S.4.5 of IMPD</p> <p>The current specification for RO7113755 (GDC-0077) release and stability testing is in accordance with industry standards. The specifications will be re-evaluated as additional data become available. The specifications may be modified as more knowledge and data become available</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the justification for the specifications is acceptable?</p> <p>The justification is acceptable.</p>

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<p>2.15 Reference standards or materials</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Was the Primary reference standard used (compendial or in-house)? If in-house, batch number should be provided NO</p> <p>For pharmacopoeial APIs, is the working standard qualified against the official standard?</p> <p>For non pharmacopoeial APIs, is the primary in-house reference standard fully characterized and structurally elucidated with purity determined using an absolute procedure?</p> <p>Refer to section S.4 of the IMPD</p> <p>Batch 3141203 was qualified to serve as the reference standard</p>
	<p>Comment</p> <p>Is the suitable reference standard adequately described?</p> <p>The reference standard is adequately described</p>
<p>2.16 Stability</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the proposed shelf-life/retest period and storage conditions of the drug substance mentioned?</p> <p>Is the summary of stability studies in support of the proposed shelf-life submitted?</p> <p>Refer to section 4 of the IMPD</p> <p>The proposed retest period is 36 months with the storage label "Do not store above</p>

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	<p>30 °C, protect from light”</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the stability for the drug substance satisfactory and properly described for all the relevant manufacturing processes?</p> <p>The stability of the products has been described.</p>
<p>3. Drug Product (P)</p>	
<p>3.1 Description and composition of the IMP</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the qualitative and quantitative composition of the IMP stated?</p> <p>Refer to table P.1-1 of the IMPD</p> <p>The drug product is composition has been provided</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the description and composition adequate?</p> <p>The description and composition are acceptable.</p>
<p>3.2 Pharmaceutical development</p>	<p>Workspace</p>

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	<p>Are studies conducted to establish that the route of administration, dosage form, the formulation, manufacturing process, container-closure system, microbiological attributes and usage instructions appropriate for the purpose specified in the application?</p> <p>Refer to page 174 of the IMPD</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the pharmaceutical development adequately described?</p> <p>The pharmaceutical development has been adequately described</p>
<p>3.3 Manufacturers</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Information about all manufacturers involved (drug substance, drug product, placebo, etc) and evidence of GMP (GMP certificates):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name and address of the site • Function <p>Roche</p> <p>F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd</p> <p>Grenzacherstrasse 124</p> <p>4070 Basel, Switzerland</p> <p>Manufacture and Quality Control Testing</p>

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	<p>Companies that do Primary and secondary packaging have also been provided refer to table P.3.1-1</p>
<p>3.4 Description of the manufacturing process and process controls</p>	<p>Comment</p> <p>Are the manufacturing sites clearly identified?</p> <p>Yes</p> <hr/> <p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the manufacturing process including critical steps and in-process controls mentioned and fully described?</p> <p>Refer to section P.3.3 of the IMPD</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Is the manufacturing process and process control adequately described?</p> <p>Clearly described the manufacturing process and process control</p>
<p>3.5 Controls of critical steps and intermediates</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are the controls of critical steps and intermediates adequately described?</p> <p>Refer to P.3.4 of the IMPD</p> <p>No critical steps were identified. The drug product was manufactured under a standard process.</p> <p>No intermediates in drug product manufacturing.</p>

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	<p>Comment</p> <p>This is acceptable</p>
<p>3.6 Process validation and/or evaluation</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are the validation processes adequately described?</p> <p>Refer to section P.3.5 of the IMPD</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>Satisfactory</p>
<p>3.7 Excipients</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Are the specifications and acceptance criteria adequate?</p> <p>Are the analytical procedures adequately described and validated?</p> <p>Are the specifications of the excipients provided and limits satisfactory?</p> <p>Is the safety information on transmissible spongiform encephalopathies provided for excipients of animal origin?</p> <p>Refer to section P.4 of the IMPD</p> <p>The excipients utilized in the production of RO7113755 film-coated tablets, in both 3 mg and 9 mg strengths, adhere to compendial standards, except for the film-coating mixture.</p>

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	<p>The components used in the film-coating mixture are all compendial. Lactose is the only excipient of human or animal origin used in the manufacture of the RO7113755 film-coated tablets, 3 mg and 9 mg. Lactose is derived from cow's milk. No novel excipients are used in the manufacture of the RO7113755 3 mg and 9 mg film-coated tablets</p>
	<p>Comment</p>
	<p>Satisfactory</p>
<p>3.8 Control of the drug products</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the data for representative batch analyses provided for all the relevant manufacturing process, and for each drug product manufacturer?</p> <p>Is the information provided for impurities acceptable including additional impurities/degradants that are not part of the drug substance?</p> <p>Refer to P.5.4</p> <p>Data for representative batch analyses has been provided</p>
	<p>Comment</p>
	<p>Satisfactory specifications for the drug product, including appropriate limits, are proposed</p>
	<p>Are the analytical methods adequately described?</p>
	<p>Specifications for the drug product including limits are submitted</p>

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<p>3.9 Container closure system</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the container closure system for the drug product properly characterized and suitable?</p> <p>The primary packaging for the clinical supply is a blister pack containing aluminium lidding and aluminum cold-forming film.</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Integrity for it to maintain stability</p> <p>Satisfactory</p>
<p>3.10 Stability</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the proposed shelf-life and storage conditions of the IMP stated?</p> <p>Is there a summary of stability studies provided in support of the proposed shelf-life?</p> <p>Comment whether trends or out of specifications results were observed</p> <p>The proposed shelf life is 36 months with the storage label "do not store above 30°C, protect from light"</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>The drug product has undergone appropriate stability tests</p> <p>The products have undergone stability studies and the data has been submitted.</p>

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<p>3.11 Solvents for reconstitution/dilution</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is information on solvents for reconstitution provided?</p> <p>Not provided (NA)</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>ICH reference</p> <p>NA</p>
<p>4. Comparator</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>List the comparators</p> <p>Is the data provided for the comparator acceptable (use the assessment above for the product from Section 3.1 to 3.11)</p> <p>Not provided</p> <hr/> <p>Comment</p> <p>Not applicable if product is registered in Uganda</p> <p>Not provided</p>
<p>5. Placebo</p>	<p>Workspace</p> <p>List the placebo</p>

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	<p>Is the data provided for the placebo acceptable (use the assessment above for the product Section 3.1 to 3.11)</p> <p>Refer to page 237 of the IMPD</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>Submitted information on placebo is acceptable</p>
6. Labelling	<p>Workspace</p> <p>Is the proposed labelling in line with national requirements?</p> <p>Comment</p> <p>No sample label seen in the IMPD</p>
Other	<p>None</p>

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Evaluator's final observations/Queries/Request for additional information:

Applicant should provide justification for only reporting SAE until 30 days following maintenance therapy.

Applicant should clarify if the SAEs reported to the sponsor beyond the reporting period (after the final dose of maintenance therapy) will be reported to NDA as well.

Objective measures for causality assessment should be provided.

Applicant should clarify what the next course of action is in case the participant disease progresses (treatment failure)

PI to Submit the following

- 1. Peer reviewed articles*
- 2. Duly signed clinical trial agreement.*
- 3. Professional indemnity cover*
- 4. A monitoring plan for the study*
- 5. Data management plan*
- 6. Accreditation certificate for Uganda Cancer Institute laboratory.*
- 7. A valid accreditation certificate for Cellcarta Sint-BAVOSTRAAT 78-80 B-2610 Belgium*
- 8. PACTR registration number*
- 9. An updated IB*

Applicant to clearly clarify on the exact countries (other sites) that will implement this study.

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The seventh objective on characterising PK of trastuzumab and pertuzumab could cause additional burden to the participants as it may require withdraw of more blood from participants

IDMC membership does not include a local representative

Assessor's overall conclusions on the clinical part

Category 1a (approval – nothing outstanding)

Category 2a (Not approved until certain administrative items are attended to)

Category 2b (Not approved until queries by evaluator are satisfactorily addressed)

Category 5 (Rejected for the following specific regulatory reasons)

Category 6 (Rejected for the following administrative reasons)